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Black college women's lived memories of racialization in predominantly white educational spaces: I'm Black, I'm a migrant, I'm a woman, so what?

ABSTRACT

Research on experiences of gender and racial discrimination among young, racialized college women in Europe is scarce, particularly in Spain where Black women have traditionally had a minority presence in universities. As a result of processes of social mobility, these women are now occupying higher education spaces to an unprecedented extent, where they are becoming increasingly visible. These women's experiences of gender and racial discrimination throughout the education cycle are invisible. The aim of this article is to explore the personal experiences of racialization and discrimination among Black female college students in southern Spain. Twelve in-depth interviews were conducted and analysed to shed light on the experiences of young Black female students in predominantly white educational institutions. The stories of these women show that gender and race intersect and are constructed simultaneously through interactions with their mostly white peers. These women are shown to display responses of significant resilience.

Keywords: Racialized experiences, Black women bodies, Black student women, Racism and discrimination in southern Spain.

INTRODUCTION

Following Critical Race Theory (CRT) in the educational context (Joseph-Salisbury, 2019), this case study is an attempt to give specific voice to the educational experiences of Black university women in southern Europe, particularly in Spain, as an understudied population in global perspectives on education, gender and culture and a crucial piece of contemporary European immigration. Most analyses of educational spaces and

experiences in the Spanish context have been of a generalized nature, and those that have taken women into account have been based on the experiences of white middle-class students (Ariño, 2014; Megias-Blas, 2019) which do not capture the experiences of Black women. The term Black women, following Edwards (1990), is used, in a general and political sense, as women of different ethnic and geographical origins who are the object of racism in educational spaces, and which refers, in a descriptive way, to the women interviewed, and the term they used with respect to themselves in the Afro-Caribbean sense. Their descriptive preference is followed.

There is a growing need to examine the lived realities of racialization and discrimination among Black female college students through their experiences in educative spaces, predominantly white educational institutions (primary schools, secondary schools, and universities), by means of their personal accounts. These three educational stages were chosen in order to conduct a retrospective analysis of the interviewees' experiences from childhood to young adulthood. The aim is to collect data on the changing process of racialisation (Suki et al., 2010) in order to illuminate the social conditions and circumstances of Black women in universities, from 19 to 31 years of age, in their educational contexts in Spain. I want to show how these women learn about and respond to how racialisation and engendering are fostered in these educational stages, as well as how they respond to multiple embodiments, and understand the meaning they have given to their educational experiences, since by then they have probably experienced discrimination and oppression at school and in society in general (Mirza, 2018). As their accounts reveal, gender and race are constructed simultaneously through processes of inequality and racism (Showumni and Tomlin, 2022) and the concept of embodiment is developed by analysing the race-gender nexus. The stories reveal the difference that comes from occupying different racial spaces, "discarding the enlightened individual model of the subject as purely disembodied, evanescent, and transcendent 'mind', where the subject is imagined in an as yet unspecified relationship with the real space." (Kyrbi, 1993). The social process and interactions are demonstrated through which Black girls are constructed as a particular disadvantaged group through the various educational stages, and how they generate responses of significant resilience.

THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Intersectionality allows us to analyse how race, gender and sexuality identities are created simultaneously with the multiple forms of oppressions and discriminations that depend on their relationship (Crenshaw, 1991; Omi and Winant, 2015). These oppressions manifest themselves through everyday sexism and racism that are reinforced through the normalisation of practices such as jokes, storytelling, generalisations or even so-called compliments, whose effects are downplayed as trivial or amusing. They are discerned in educational, family or normative institutions, where people experience race, class and gender, and become aware of how these oppressions affect their lives, who they are, their subjectivities and the specific forms of oppressions created (Essed, 2002; Hill, 2017). The stigmatizing and racist expressions that take place in educational daily life as spaces of socialization that young people go through, bear signs of an emotional wall that marks physical proximities and symbolic distances between individuals and groups (Kaplan, 2016). At the same time, *primary schools, secondary schools, and universities* are spaces where children and young people simultaneously construct and negotiate race structures and gender meanings (Hamilton et al. 2019; Showumni and Tomlin, 2022). West and Fenstermaker (2002) developed the notion of “doing gender” and “doing race” and ethnomethodologically conceptualized gender and race. These authors assigned cultural meanings to racialized bodies from the representations that were produced and circulated in schools and other social institutions. They found that at the preschool age children consciously use race and gender categories to include, exclude, or establish dominance over others in their interactions (West and Zimmerman 1987; West and Fenstermaker, 2002). *Racial socialization* defines cultural heritage and how to act in the face of hostility through a set of behaviours, attitudes, and values transmitted by parents to their children. Traditionally, the literature on racial socialisation has differentiated four types (Hughes et al., 2006), where the first, preparation for prejudice, refers to parents' efforts to prepare their children for the racism and racial discrimination they are likely to face. The second type refers to the promotion of distrust in relation to socialisation towards out-group members. The third is cultural socialisation, where parents promote racial pride in their children. The last type is egalitarianism, where families minimise or do not discuss the importance of race and try to promote values such as hard work, initiative and self-acceptance, which they believe will enable their children to succeed in life (Hughes et al., 2006). Despite the criticisms for the simplicity of this classification (Thornhill,

2016), the identification of these four types of racial socialisation allows us to understand how the experiences of young Black women in universities regarding their family's response to racist aggression may correspond to the life cycles of childhood, youth and adulthood in line with educational cycles.

Parents initiate a process of racial socialization by discussing discrimination in school with their children, warning them of the barriers they may encounter because of their ethnicity, and helping them to cope (Hughes et al. 2006; Thornhill, 2016). Some studies have found that this racial socialization has positive effects in terms of academic performance, psychological well-being, and higher self-esteem (Tang et al., 2016; Colen et al., 2019; Leath, 2020). Analysis has also been carried out on how a Black mother's critical awareness, through intimate relationships with their children, fosters resistance against beliefs, attitudes and practices that can erode Black children's confidence and health, and generates positive identity development by helping them to identify readings, images and/or behaviours as forms of racism in schools (Trent et al., 2019). Some rarely visualised everyday resistances of children to racism include modifying appearance as a strategy for negotiating race, which is a good example of the embodiment used and an important analytic tool to cope with racism (Twine, 2010; Okello et al. 2020). Nunn (2016), in her study with girls between 8–13 years old, proposes the development of empowerment programmes for Black girls to confront and respond to the degrading social experiences that permeate their daily lives and to overcome the feelings of strength and sadness they experience as Black girls. She provides evidence-based strategies to improve social support, self-efficacy, self-esteem, locus of control, optimism, and body image. These girl's groups can go through changes at the immediate level of individuals and groups, in their sense of self-hood and identity, in how they perceive their interests, and in their capacity to act. Groups can aim for the intermediate level of empowerment, in regard to the rules and relationships that prevail in the personal, social, economic, and political spheres of life. They can also exert influence more deeply, within hidden structures, which shape the existing marginalisation and disenfranchisement embedded in social realities that are perpetuated in educational practices, and reproduced over time (Kabeer 2005:27). Along with these programmes, institutional changes with feminist policies and a public social justice agenda are needed to achieve deeper levels of historical changes in gender discrimination and racism. In secondary schools, these processes of racialization to constitute Black bodies as unworthy of respect are affected by what Fraser (1997) called misrecognition—that is, institutionalized practices to deny

people the opportunity to participate equally in social life. Other studies have shown how Black girls are subject to unfair treatment related to a quite different set of stereotypes. As Collins (2000, 2009) describes, the controlling images “are designed to make racism, sexism, and poverty appear to be natural, normal, and an inevitable part of everyday life”. Black girls’ bodies were understood differently, rendered problematic, and “adultified” in distinct but still problematic ways. For example, their “assertive” behaviour has been seen as less feminine and often interpreted as aggressive (Lewis and Lewis, 2017). For Black students, secondary school means choosing between assimilating into the school culture or maintaining strong social and cultural ties to their ethnic communities. As they grow up, many eventually choose to remain within the social and cultural folds of their ethnic enclaves because of emotional ties or responsibilities to family and friends (Sullivan and Cross, 2016). In the transition to adulthood, college becomes a space of racialization where peer groups interact and class differences are apparently blurred. However, some studies have shown how many Black college students begin to feel that they are unwanted on campus (Harper 2009; Strayhorn, 2009; Lo, 2017). Other authors examine the racialized experiences of students of colour in higher education, and found that they experienced feelings of frustration, anger, and fatigue in their processes of racialization (Mizra 2006; Hubain et al. 2014; Tomlin, 2022).

Black women respond to processes of racialization in many and diverse ways (Gardner, 1995; Gonzalez-Sobrino and Goss, 2017). Some authors have analysed how bodies resist and can be considered places of empowerment and the agency of racialized women when faced with street harassment, and silence as a form of agency to respond to the difference of power (Hochschild, 1995; Hakim, 2011). Responding to injustices is part of the process of consciousness-raising or individual empowerment. In this respect, the distinction made by Kristina Thalhammer (2007) about the necessary conditions "to become courageous resisters as a lifestyle or to courageously resist situationally " is important. In order to be able to exercise courageous resistance, there are a number of external factors and individual conditions that make it possible, such as socialisation; the type of country one lives in; social norms; and the family values one grew up with. It matters whether a person only identifies with an "us" group when it is considered homogenous, or whether their "us" group includes other people in addition to people who look alike, whether because of differences in race, ethnicity or gender. The more diverse the "we" group is, the less inclined it will be to engage in demeaning,

exclusionary or discriminatory behaviour against someone who does not look exactly alike. External factors include whether people become aware of injustice and how they respond to prevent or enable harm to themselves and others, for example, the existence of potentially resistant ties with others, exposure to role models or membership of religious communities, among others.

Internal factors include awareness of what is wrong, the attitude people have towards authority, or towards helping others and those they consider members of their group (Thalhammer et al., 2007).

The idea of silence and the need to 'act white' has been sustained in the process of racialization and is understood as a means of embodied agency to naturalize such asymmetry], and that silence and acting white do not form part of the process of empowerment or strategic choices (Molyneux, 1998; de Certeau, 2000; Showunmi, 2019), but can be defined as imposed tactics to counter situations of discrimination and violence.

METHODS AND DATA

This is qualitative empirical research to study experiences of Black university women students in Southern Spain through their narratives of events, looking at how these women identify behaviours and accounts related with their racialization process that reveal the complexity of race in educational spaces. Through semi-structured interviews, these details of the object of study are captured, manifesting the value of a micro-perspective. Reconstruction of interviewees memories trace the discourse, practices and spaces in which and through which the past, specifically in their educational processes from primary school to college, is made present and meaningful (Kidron, 2009) and through which the collective of a community produces and reproduces the memory of the past (Connerton, 1989). A critical race methodology in educational research is used, focused on micro-aggressions, intersectionality, sexualization, embodiment to illustrate how these played out in the lives of these women, to question the often normalised and naturalised racial and racist processes, underpinned by the construction of white bodies that is defined as white supremacy and its institutions, such as educational institutions (Joseph-Salisbury, 2019).

The participants were selected by means of snowball sampling. The selection criteria were to be Black, female and a university student. The reason for selecting these participants was, despite the evidence indicating that racism in education at both an

institutional and a personal level affects pupils' dispositions to learning, resulting in disproportionate numbers of Black girls being excluded from school (Houston, 2018; Tomlin et al. 2019), they have nevertheless reached University and have had experiences in all educational stages, overcoming these barriers through various strategies. Hearing narratives of “othered” communities about effective action against racism in education provides the rationale for the stories of these young Black women. The participants comprised twelve Black ~~racialized~~ women college students, from 19 to 31 years old. All of them are students at the public University in Granada although one of them had one year’s experience in a private university in the same city, which did not significantly affect her experience. All of them shared experiences of inequality and discrimination due to the racialization of their bodies, and without significant differences between the interviewees. At the moment there are Black Spanish college students, but they are a minority and Spanish universities have not produced details of racial composition.

The contact strategy consisted in approaching female students on campus, explaining the research study to them and our interest in conducting an interview. The interviews were conducted individually by the author at different times with each of the interviewees at a university faculty, with the aid of one undergraduate student. The assistance consisted of conducting the interviews along with the author, since their presence increased the interviewees’ trust, as they belonged to their peer group. The names of people and places have been changed to ensure the confidentiality of the data, as agreed with the interviewees.

CONTEXT: WHY SPAIN?

The study was conducted in a public university of Andalusia, in the south of Spain. There are 367,250 Afro-descendant residents in Spain (INE, 2019). Despite the presence of a Black population, the Spanish government does not record statistics on the ethnic and racial background of its population (Minority Rights Group, 2022). It was not until 2000 that ethnic origin and race became categories on which the discourses and educational practices that foster the creation of power relations are based, problematizing them in terms of threat and danger (Olmos, 2010). As Mizra (2018) states, “Black female subjectivity and identity and the form of their “difference” is systematically organized through social relations and economic, political and practical structures [...] in which structures of power reproduce social divisions in the everyday lives of women of colour”. The interviewees' schools are places where Blackness is

displaced and whiteness is the norm, and where racial and gender distinctions shape Black women's experiences in places of learning. Previous research shows that the schooling of young immigrants and minorities takes place in centres with little motivation for academic success, in schools of low prestige, etc... and how the Spanish educational system fails in inclusion, and that ethnic origin leads to exclusion and bullying at school which causes families to opt for a different centre in quest of protection (Pámies, 2013; Hernández-Castilla, 2020). Despite these important contributions, there are few works that address the first-person experiences of Black students. This research tries to contribute to filling this gap in the Spanish context.

RESULTS

The first experience: keeping distance and racial socialization

Schools are public spaces where socialization, one of the most important processes of social life, takes place (Berger and Luckman, 1966) but also the first places where “Black bodies are expelled from the white social body” (Ahmed, 2002, 59) and where hate is manifested through encounters of inscribed bodies and in the reconstitution of the bodily space (Lorde, 1984). Most of the women interviewed described being insulted and suffering racist comments in their first experience where their bodies were inscribed in a Black racialized way. When referring to their experiences in primary school, several interviewees stated that white pupils become racists when they align themselves with other white bodies, which they feel are more similar to their own, and against Black bodies, which they view as being apart from them. For example, at the age of seven, Sara reconstituted her racialized bodily space when she suffered an aggression that, in theory at least, was not considered a crime and for which the perpetrators were not held accountable. Furthermore, the school minimized the importance of the aggression and justified it on the grounds that one of the minors involved had family problems. Such violence is normalized through slow, non-existent or violent responses, lack of public assistance, and many other ways that constitute violence in themselves. The legal system has generally defined sexism as based on an unspoken reference to the injustices faced by all women (including white women), while racism refers to the injustices faced by all Blacks (including men) and other people of colour. Frequent forms of violence and discrimination against Black women often do not fit into the legal categories of “racism” or “sexism,” but are rather a combination of both (Crenshaw, 1991). This situation means that Black women are frequently legally “invisible” and left without legal recourse; hence the disaffection of our interviewees with institutions in

general, such as the police and/or the judiciary, and with educational institutions in particular. Such disaffection can be perceived in the feelings of frustration and anger of Sara's mother, who finally moved her daughter to another school after one month (Nunn, 2016):

I started here at Ave Maria School, and I lasted a month. I came face-to-face with reality there. I had a friend who was also Colombian, Nancy, who was older than me and who slept in the boarding school. One day I came home and said "Mum, I want to sleep over at Nancy's, we're going to have a pyjama party" and my mum didn't want me to go but I insisted so much that she said "OK, you can go." I packed my backpack . . . with all the matching Barbie towels and a cell phone to keep in touch with my mum because she worked so much. That night I stayed at the boarding school and all of sudden, through the window I see like a fire in the courtyard. I went down all happy to see [what was going on] ... Some kids had taken my things, my Barbie towel, and had made a fire with them... The next day one of the kids who started it called me names, yelled at me. I still remember it as if it was yesterday, and of course I called my mum... I said "Mum, a kid insulted me, he called me such and such" ... When my mum went to talk [to the school authorities] they told her it was a kid with family problems. I think this is the only time I have seen my mum so angry that she said "I'm going to smack that kid." (Sara, 26 years old)

Sara also referred to how Black bodies are expelled from the white social body (Lorde 1984) and described how, in a tactic of self-defence, she joined up with another Black student to support her:

Then I went to the Rafael Costa School which was in the north of the city and I think I lasted a year there, too. There were only two of us Black girls. The other girl was from Senegal but she never spoke... And they always laughed at her because she suffered... she had a nasal problem and always had a cold... I always gave her Kleenex. I'll never forget that scene of "here, have a Kleenex." (Sara, 26 years old)

Different processes of racial socialization are fostered when confronted with such discrimination. In Sara's case, her mother moved her to another school again

(Hernández- Castilla, 2020). By doing so, Sara's mother taught her how to respond to such situations, how to be strong, and how to act in a racist society, and Sara gradually acquired the capacity for situational courageous resistance (Thornhill, 2016) from a young age:

I lasted a year because the environment wasn't one of learning but of social inclusion in the sense that, let's include them because they're poor, they're excluded but they don't need to learn, just to adapt; and my mother was not very keen on that, so I changed schools and went to San Pedro. (Sara, 26 years old)

In Beatriz's case, as part of her racial socialization, her mother taught her how racism and discrimination would be a part of her life and the conflicts she would face:

It's true that my mother has always prepared me for life from a very young age. I remember her telling me, "You have to work harder. If there's a job, and both of you are equally qualified, they'll give it to the other person because they're white." . . . My mother always told me: "If there's a fight, they'll call someone stupid and you'll be called Black." (Beatriz, 20 years old)

The process of racialization in primary schools includes merging all Black bodies into one by homogenizing and confusing them, as the experience of another interviewee, Mayte, reveals. Although she normalizes the issue by claiming that it is not a problem of racism, Mayte's experience is an example of how racial stereotyping debases Black identities. Underlying these stereotypes are false interpretations of how certain racial groups should behave, see themselves, and exist within society (Tomlin, 2022). This essentialism constructs Blackness as something different (and often inferior to) other racial groups, and might have a detrimental effect on Mayte, who may not identify as Black and/or with these symbols of Blackness (Omi and Winant, 2015; Hubain et al., 2016):

I got to fourth grade and was the only Black girl in school. There was another girl who was lighter than me but she obviously had Black parents and they always confused us. She was almost in ESO [middle school] but they always confused us. They called me by her name and they called her Mayte. But I never had any problems with racism there. (Mayte, 31 years old)

As Felisa's experience shows, in this process of bodily racialization, the Black body is

not only interpreted as being dirty, as a body from which to keep distance, “but the re-forming of the contours of the white body, through the very affective gestures that enable withdrawal from the Black body’s cohabitation in a given social space” (Ahmed 2002: 61), in this case, school:

*“Coffee! Coffee . . . coffee! Your skin is very dirty, don’t touch me.”
Yeah, they often make those kinds of comments, racist comments.
Those kids and their parents are like, “They’re just kids talking!” But
you [the parents] really should have put them right from the beginning,
because if you don’t put them right when they’re kids, then later on . .
. (Felisa, 18 years old)*

Secondary School: Normalization of Racism and Distancing from The Bodily Social Space

The transition to secondary education is characterized by social bodily distancing between racialized and white bodies. Secondary schools are the setting where the social distance between Black and white social bodies is marked with a type of racial socialisation where distrust of out-group members is promoted (Hughes et al., 2006). Essentialism continues at this stage of education, where Black bodies are reduced to being believably Black of the kind “she needed to wear African clothing and beat a drum” (Hubain et al. 2016: 958). Identification with a homogeneous "we" group explains this stage where situational courageous resistance tends to occur because of social distance from the out-group (Thalhammer et al., 2007) and because of the characteristics of socialisation characterised by mistrustful out-group members (Hughes et al., 2006),

In my class, it’s not that they were racist or anything, but you notice the comments. In class they say Africa and everyone looks at you. And like Africa is a country, so you feel identified every time they talk about Africa. On top of that, I was the only Black girl at the school, I was the centre of attention. White people wouldn’t come up to me unless they wanted me to talk about Africa or Guinea. They’d ask me, “Do you eat chicken in Africa?” (Maria, 20 years old).

Microaggressions as part of everyday racism are continuously reiterated, they become culturally normalized and end up functioning as systematic discrimination against minorities, which reinforce majority privilege (Lopez, 2003; Essed and Muhr, 2018; Essed, 2019;). Disparaging stereotypes that portray Black racialized women as

subordinate savages who do not know how to behave socially and must be civilized are also commonplace (hooks, 1996; Ahmed, 2002; Osha, 2014):

The problem is you haven't raised your child properly . . . so she learns how to behave, this is Spain, this is Europe, she's not in an African country, she's already used to what she does in her country (Felisa, 18 years old)

The women who were interviewed also shared accounts of how they tried to fit in, go unnoticed, and engage in activities like their peers by changing their physical appearance and erotic capital in an attempt to avoid the negative stereotypes associated with what is assumed to be Black (Egleston and Halsell 2009). Modifying appearance as a strategy for negotiating race and racism is a good example of the embodiment used to cope with racist situations (Twine, 2010; Showunmi, 2019).

Before, well, you turn fifteen and say I want to be just like them. Things like when you start to straighten your hair . . . or maybe forget my language and not want to speak it. I felt kind of ashamed. But why? It's your identity and that's it. You work on it... There will be things you don't like, that's normal! But that's it, don't internalize that racism you suffer outside . . . because it'll kill you. (Paula, 21 years old)

At this life stage, these women's family and support networks play a critical role in the self-affirmation of their identity as Hughes et al. (2006) explained regarding cultural socialization, where parents promote racial pride in their sons and daughters. As the interviews revealed, these women attached great importance to their support networks in times of personal and identity conflict, although in response to what Hughes et al. (2006) referred to as the fourth stage of racial socialisation, egalitarianism, where families do not discuss or minimise the importance of race, they preferred not to discuss the racist attacks and violence they experienced so as not to particularly worry their mothers. This process of racial socialisation diminishes as young women find their own ways of coping with experiences of discrimination:

Most of the time I just keep it to myself, but because I don't see the need to tell anyone. For example, my mother, who is very nervous... her blood pressure might go up, so I prefer not to say anything. (Maria, 20 years old)

Higher Education: Sexual Objectification

At university, the relations between Black bodies and white bodies undergo a change. According to all those interviewed, their bodies are no longer expelled from the white social body and the distances are smaller. The students interviewed believe that negative social labelling and stereotyping of Black people are part of the barriers they have to deal with as young Black women in the higher education system. Although they acknowledge that there is greater awareness of the African context at this educational level, the perceptions of Black people remain highly stereotyped.

The narratives and discussions that emerged during the individual interviews confirmed that many of the students were deeply concerned about how they are viewed by society at large. They felt that society as a whole is, to some extent, surprised that Black students go to college to pursue a degree, because they are not expected to be able to do so (Mizra, 2006, 2009, 2018):

The first day I got to class, everybody was whispering and looking at me . . . like, “What the fuck is she doing here? And . . . does she have money to pay for this? I guess, too, because that school is private and it’s expensive. They probably think how strange, “Black women don’t go to private schools” ... But it wasn’t just about the money, in some activities we had to shake hands, and that disgusted some people. Now we get along and they hug me, and I joke and say “Hey, don’t push it” it’s a matter of getting used to it. (Raquel, 23 years old)

At university, processes of racialization are shaped by their association with racially categorized abilities. The Blackness of women’s bodies is perceived by peers as having a significant aptitude for sensuality and sexuality. This perception is shared by all of the interviewees and becomes increasingly normalized the more experiences they have both on campus and in their relationships with male and female classmates.

Yesterday, for example, I walked into a class and heard “Look, that Black girl is hot.” It was an 18-year-old kid, I mean, young... He sat down in front of me and said “Hi!, hi!, how’s it going?” and I said “Fine” and he said “Are you from here?” and I said “No, I’m in fourth year”. “Ah, from fourth year, and what are you doing here?”, like trying you know, but he kept looking at me like that with that up and down look, looking at my breasts instead of looking at my face and I

was covered up so it's very, very strange if I see that no, there's no connection. (Mayte, 31 years old)

The representation of Black women's bodies in contemporary popular culture often subverts or criticizes images of Black women's sexuality that has formed part of the cultural apparatus of racism since the 19th century and is still pervasive today (Gilman, 1985; hooks, 1996). The women interviewed describe the fascination that their bodies awoken in their male classmates:

I realized here that being Black and being here was going to be a problem in terms of emotional issues because we're very sexualized... The guys are very aware of that . . . because you're Black, you're Latina, you're Colombian so you must be a [sexual] volcano... [When you're] on a date and want to have something more than sex with a person, you shouldn't have to bring up those kinds of things, you should ask me what I think about history, politics or "hey, remember that in such and such a year such and such a thing happened?" and what I think, right? Go beyond sex. (Sara, 26 years old).

Performativity and Adulthood: Tactics for Coping with Inequality

The young women's experiences of racialization in these educational spheres are the product of racialized and gendered power asymmetries but also what Mizra terms as *radical sites of resistance and refutation* (2006). The young women's experiences of racialization in these educational spheres, but also in what Mizra terms as *radical sites of resistance and refutation* (2006), are the product of racialized and gendered power asymmetries. Their stories reflect two types of tactical response, through which specific ways of embodiment are used (Twine, 2010) to cope with the violence inflicted upon them, that require individual preparation and awareness. Both are employed as a way to identify and fit in with the predominant group in order to reduce heterogeneity to homogeneity and multiplicity to unity (Lugones, 1994), to minimize the significance of race and to promote values of self-acceptance, (Hughes et al., 2006). The first is the aesthetic labour to modify how they dress or wear their hair, that is, the transformation of certain elements of their erotic capital (Hakim, 2011) to adapt to the prevailing style in the educational settings of which they form a part. In this case, the tactic aims to reduce erotic capital through aesthetic and emotional labour (Hoschild, 1983); specifically, the component of erotic capital concerning social presentation. In the sense of Bourdieu (2000), this aesthetic labour seeks to fulfil the need to acquire a body

whose dimensions, style of dress, and bearing reflect the cultural meanings one wishes to convey (Moreno Pestaña and Bruquetas, 2012). Faced with outside gazes that sexualize or criticize, the interviewees said that they adopted strategies such as wearing baggy clothes and putting their hair up so as to go unnoticed:

If I'm going out at night I try to look as masculine as possible. I change the way I walk, I walk a little more like a man because I've had altercations at night, like, I have to run away, I have to ask for help and nobody does anything. So it's like, if I camouflage myself to be a little bit more manly, nothing's going to happen to me. I've noticed that when I wear my hair natural it draws too much attention to me; and I don't like to be the centre of attention... I usually tend to keep a low profile to not draw too much attention to myself (Raquel, 23 years old)

The second tactic, silence and normalization, is related to experience and awareness acquired with age. Silence is understood as a form of embodied agency and another form of “aesthetic labour” performed to cope with everyday racism, but not as a means of empowerment. According to the women interviewed, in their transition to adulthood they became aware of the situation of structural inequality, accepted it, and relied on silence as a response. This tactic reduces frustration, transforming it into a habit (Day, 1997). As in other studies such as that of Day (1994: 742-765) on the consequences of fear and crime prevention in the lives of college women in California, the interviewees describe violence and insults as “the natural state of things”:

Here I encountered another struggle. The fact that I'm a woman, an immigrant, and Black meant that I had to deal with it in a different way... My teenage years until I was 20, 21 were a struggle of me saying “I want to leave, what am I doing here?” I've spent long nights crying and saying “But why does all this happen to me?” “Doesn't it happen to anyone else, where's the karma for all those bad people?” It's been really hard. But let's say that the way I interact, the way I behave, the way I justify certain things has changed. I'm not so submissive anymore. . . I'm Black, I'm a migrant, I'm a woman, so what? And you don't have to make me feel small to help me, just the opposite. (Mayte, 31 years old)

Both tactics, which are the product of social and family support, are the ways in which

individuals deal with everyday situations of discrimination and violence that have no impact at the structural level, where naturalized representations of Black racialized women of African descent persist. Unlike strategies, tactics correspond to practical choices that cannot change social structures that favour emancipation or empowerment (Molyneux 1986) and are dependent on circumstances (De Certeau, 2000).

CONCLUSIONS

This work has explored Black college women's lived memories of racialization in predominantly white educational spaces throughout their lives. These experiences have shown how racial identities are constructed among peer groups in primary school, secondary school, and college through a process of racialization that goes beyond skin colour. In these educational spaces, racialization is a process by which their bodies—first as Black girls and then as Black women—are invested with meaning over time.

The results are consistent with the scientific literature on the experiences of young women who have been Black racialized in these educational spaces. From the age of 8–9 years, Black bodies begin to be expelled from the white social body in interactions with peer groups at school. These initial experiences of discrimination lead to processes of racial socialization through which mothers teach girls to cope with discrimination. In secondary school, the most significant experience is the social distancing between Black and white social bodies, while this social distance diminishes at university and the sexualization of Black women's bodies becomes part of the racialization process.

The accounts presented here show the inscribed bodies of young, Black university women who have increasingly traumatic experiences and who, through social and family support, adopt two

types of individual tactics to cope with the daily violence they suffer. Firstly, when faced with criticism and outside gazes, they engage in aesthetic labour to adapt their style and appearance. Secondly, the women interviewed respond to discrimination and violence with silence and normalization, thus reducing their feelings of frustration. Neither tactic succeeds in transforming the established order through bodily agency, as their bodies are structurally disempowered, but do provide demonstrations of stories of love through the relationships with their mothers and other family members to reclaim another meaning of education.

These individual tactics to counter the normalization of violence against Black

university women highlight the need to collectively address vulnerabilities related to racialization. This will require collective action and a supportive institutional environment, as well as the design and implementation of public policies and regulations aimed at achieving greater levels of structural empowerment.

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